

Engineering emotional product identities in high-luxury vehicles

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5th. International Conference on Design and Emotion, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden. September 2006.

Paper submitted under the Brand and Identity theme.

Abstract

This paper aims to describe one avenue of a programme of research into brand identity and its relationship to engineering product concepts at Bentley Motors Limited. We start with a review of the automotive market place, showing that it has become 'commoditised'; functional product properties have reached a level of technical parity and distributional saturation and thus branding and style have become the new 'attractive product qualities'. We will discuss how within the high-luxury and 'pinnacle' automotive markets, brand associations - personal beliefs, values and emotions, and brand identity, as expressed through the lineage of product design - are especially salient in creating differentiation and commercial advantage. This results in automakers' seeking brand-focused design and engineering strategies in order to promote brand identities through multi-sensory product property stimuli.

We respond to this background with one of a series of studies into the lineage of product properties and vehicle features at Bentley Motors. Drawing upon contemporary research from cognitive science and marketing into concept identity recognition and categorisation, quantitative and qualitative data from focus groups is analysed to propose diagnostic scales of 'typicality' for vehicle properties. From this we demonstrate that the identification and diagnosis of 'Bentleyness', the perceived fit between the brand and its products, varies and is weighted for different product features.

Key words;

Branding, Engineering Attribute Management, Categorisation, Prototype Theory.

Introduction

This paper describes one avenue of research conducted into brand identity as expressed through the products produced by Bentley Motors Limited in the high-luxury and pinnacle automotive market segments. We start with a review of this market and its prevalent trends with the aim of demonstrating that today, branding influences major product differentiation, and especially so, in luxury vehicles. We then discuss the importance of the evolution of multi-sensory product properties in defining a 'lineage' and 'authenticity' that supports accurate and differentiated brand recognition by consumers. Evidence from cognitive science is presented to support an analytical method for brand / product property diagnosis. We then test this proposition with a focus group study of Bentley 'heritage' products with qualitative and quantitative data analysis. Finally, we discuss the results of the analysis indicating that product properties that stimulate a perceived fit between the brand and its product are weighted and vary between different vehicle properties and features.

Automotive Product Uniformity and the Rise of the Brand

Product uniformity and 'commoditisation' is a contemporary concept in the automotive marketplace; differentiation between the product offerings of different vehicle manufacturers has been narrowing for a number of decades as industry practices, and the technological knowledge-base has matured and globalised. Product performance (power, acceleration, ride, handling, braking), quality levels, reliability, durability and safety levels, are no longer a competitive influence exclusive to the more expensive and luxurious marques. They have reached a level of 'technical parity', converging to become a minimum requirement of the consumer visiting any showroom. (Accenture 2005; Antlitz et. al. 2004; Cornet & Krieger 2005; Di Riso et. al. 2005; Gruntegs et. al. 2005).

When evaluating the marketplace, we can see that which the consumer expects from a product can be defined as 'quality', being either objective; '*expressed by a state of physical fulfilment*' (eg: the product meets its targets; is functional) or subjective; '*expressed by user satisfaction*' (eg: the way the product meets its targets; is delightful or appealing) (Kano et. al. 1984). Kano's model for quality, how satisfaction relates to achievement in objective and subjective states, has been adapted more recently to give an insight into the natural cycle of technical

change and its diffusion (Schutte 2005), which can be applied to the experience of automotive consumers. Product quality, safety and reliability attributes, were once ‘attractive’ to automotive consumers, when they were unexpected against normal performance and were rarely obtainable (Fig.1.). In the past 25 years, however, technical parity and distributional saturation have been reached, making them normal and obtainable, thus moving them from ‘attractive’ to ‘must-be’ qualities in consumers product expectations (Fig.2.).

Fig 1. Kano Model (Kano et. al. 1984) with examples of ‘Attractive qualities’ in automotive products in the 1980’s.

Fig 2. Kano Model (following the adaptation by Schutte 2005) with examples of ‘Must-be qualities’ in automotive products in 2006.

Concurrently, manufacturing efficiency and design and development effectiveness have been realised through automakers' global acquisitions and consolidation. For example, the global number of independent automakers reduced from 52 in the 1960's to 30 in 1980 to 12 today (Accenture 2005). Efficiencies delivered by consolidation have lead automakers to respond faster to evolving consumer demands for products that reflect more closely consumers' personal values, experiences and beliefs. Product differentiation, in terms of model variants, style variations and lifestyle types has grown steadily, leading to models that satisfy ever-smaller market niches. For example, in the US between 1994 and 2004 there was a 69% increase in major variants of car models; the average number of models per brand increasing from 20 to 34 (Accenture 2005). However, we can see, in performance terms, *'beneath the beautiful and burley surfaces...cars are growing increasingly alike'* (Antlitz et. al. 2004).

What then, are the new 'attractive qualities' for the consumer in the automotive marketplace? There is significant evidence that the brand, its evocative associations and the self-expression of values that it affords, are the new product differentiators, and the battle-ground upon which commercial advantage is won. (Fig. 3.) As Stephen Bayley explains; *'a brand is that collection of associations and expectations possessed by successful products'* (Bayley 2005). The importance of the brand has risen *'in direct proportion to the decline in other differentiating attributes'* (Gruntegs et al 2005). Indeed, profitability, and even survival, increasingly depends on the strength of the company's brand image. Automakers focusing on the historical 'attractive qualities' of safety, for example, in their attribute-driven marketing campaigns, have seen their market share correspondingly decline (Cornet & Krieger 2005). Consumer research supports the tendency towards more emotional, brand related preferred attributes; the market researchers McKinsey have identified that criteria such as 'trendy', 'exterior styling', 'interior styling' and 'makes me feel attractive' are all included in the top 10 most important purchasing criteria for mid-sized sedans in Japan, Germany and the US (Cornet & Krieger 2005).

Fig 3. Kano Model (Kano et. Al. 1984) with examples of ‘Attractive qualities’ and ‘Must-be qualities’ for automotive products in 2006.

In response to the rise of the brand, automakers have shifted their focus from a singular approach to brand development (advertising communications) to broader and more diverse brand focused-design, development, manufacturing, and product extension and marketing strategies. In R&D divisions, developing products that possess properties that enhance the brand are at the heart of engineering attribute-management processes. Simultaneously the manufacturing hub is becoming centred on a decreasing number of ‘mega-suppliers’, who provide high-value standardised vehicle modules to the automakers assembly plants, whilst the automakers themselves *‘focus on the technologies and modules most critical to enhancing their brands’* (Dannenberg & Kleinhans 2004). Retreating to their core competencies, automakers will reduce their share of vehicle value creation, on average, from 35% to 23% between 2002 and 2015, Mercer research predicts. This shift is anticipated to be most noticeable with mass-market brands like Nissan and Chrysler, but premium brands like BMW are also expected to reduce their share to around 26%. Global automotive value creation by 2015 is anticipated to be around €903 billion per annum, with the suppliers accountable for around €700 billion (Dannenberg & Kleinhans 2004).

High-luxury and 'Pinnacle' brands

The high-luxury automotive segment, (cars selling for over €150,000), and 'pinnacle' automotive segment (cars selling for over €220,000) are markets where the importance of the brand, its associations and values, in relationship to value creation, is distinct. For global conglomerates, luxury brands are their flagships and centres of core competence (Dannenberg & Kleinhans 2004); *'for a manufacturer, possession of evocative brands is now an asset much more valuable than ownership of industrial real estate or even access to technology'* (Bayley 2005, describing Aston Martin). For consumers participating in these markets, their transport needs are a reflection of their self-expressions and values rather than the utility of getting from 'A to B' (Taylor 2003). Consumers will typically own a collection of cars and when considering another will exercise their facility to choose, maybe, between a car, or as easily, a boat, a painting or new holiday home (Hallmark, in Autoweb 2002).

Within these segments, there is a select group of established brands that operate exclusively within it; Aston Martin, Ferrari, Lamborghini, Rolls-Royce, Bentley, and more recently, the re-launch of Bugatti. Also players within these segments are established brands which cross-over into lower price segments; for example, Porsche and Mercedes-Benz. Common to these examples are rich, emotionally inspired and clearly recognisable brand identities built on decades of luxury and sporting heritage. Automakers attempting to break into these segments can quickly hit consumer-acceptance barriers if they do not possess established, recognisable and congruent brand identities to support the proposition. DaimlerChrysler have been striving to found Maybach as a credible pinnacle luxury product since 2003. Maybach's proposition has been based on technical excellence and high specifications (functional properties) as the brand bears little consumer recognition value outside Germany (lacking recognised associative product or brand attributes) (Eisenstein 2004). Consequently, despite these segments enjoying a volume increase between 2000 and 2004, in the UK, for example, of over 160% (source; www.JATO.com) (see Fig. 4.), Maybach have struggled to reach their sales targets, and are now publicly acknowledging that their initial targets were unrealistic and that the brand position may need adjusting (Eisenstein 2004; Shulinder 2005; Taylor 2003;). Conversely, Bentley's accomplishment is, in part, based on new product introduction programmes focused on product properties that support the brand's five values or 'pillars';

Racing, Driving, Power, Design and Craftmanship. These values have long-established foundations stretching from five LeMans wins in the 1930's (and more recently a sixth in 2003) through propositions of the romance of touring, torque (more salient, perhaps, than power) and style to luxury and bespoke coachwork for Royalty. Evidence suggests that brand-value driven product properties have assisted Bentley's expansion into the high-luxury segment (McCormick 2005).

Fig 4. UK car sales volume, per annum, high-luxury segment, 2000 to 2004. Source; www.JATO.com.

Brand and Product Categorisation

It is common to the established brands in the high-luxury and 'pinnacle' segments that their consumer appeal is based upon emotional associations that follow recognition of the brand, connected to, and stimulated by, distinct brand identities and embodied values that have developed over time, and have become interwoven into each product representation. For automakers striving to understand how to evoke emotional associations, in consumers' minds, which are recognised as continuing a brand lineage, it is important to have an understanding of how *specific* brand identities are perceived through the receipt of *specific* 'concept' properties. (Here the word 'concept' is used to represent both brand *and / or* branded product). There is significant research in the fields of cognitive science *and* marketing which contribute potential theories; through conjunctive hypotheses of concept access and recognition through neural network processing, concept categorisation, examples of 'best fit' to concept categories (called 'prototypicality' or 'prototype effects' ①), and concept

associations. (de Chernatony & McDonald 2003; Czellar 2002; Henderson et. al.1998; Keller 1993; Lakoff 1987). Marketing and cognitive science together propose that concept recognition is processed both consciously and sub-consciously from multi-sensory inputs *and* is influenced by experience and familiarity (Grayson & Martinec 2004; Kleine & Kernan 1991, Lindstrom 2005; Mason & Bequette 1998; Simon 1996; Smith et. al. 1988), supporting an historical, learning dimension to concept recognition competence.

Theories of the cognitive processing of concept properties that lead to the identification of an example, or set of examples, as the best example(s), or ‘prototype(s)’, within a given concept category are important here. We propose this because we find some evidence that, in part, consumer satisfaction appears to be based on such constructs within the high-luxury auto segment, design and engineering efficiency is influenced by identification accuracy and ‘fitness for purpose’ (‘fitness for brand’), and clear brand positioning benefits from it (Franzen & Bouwman 2001). Consequently, we are interested in *which* product properties are most salient in consumers identification of a product being typical of, for example, a Bentley, and how we can understand them *empirically*, so that future product proposals can be assessed for typicality during the development phase.

To help answer this, we turn to Smith, Osherson, Rips and Keane who proposed the Selective Modification Model, a method common within the literature for typicality measurement based upon cognitive judgements of similarity / dissimilarity of examples to a prototype set, based upon concept property diagnosticity values (usefulness of the property in discriminating the concept) and property saliency (strength of the property in discriminating the concept) and which is ‘...*among the only theories...to offer quantitative predictions about typicality*’ (Smith et. al. 1988). The Selective Modification Model’s primary purpose is to propose how combined concepts like PET BIRD operate, but it is useful in the first instance to provide a structure for the representation of prototype properties which can be later used in typicality

① Prototypicality; Hypotheses of cognitive processing of typicality that a concept (eg: object) being a member of a category through shared resemblances of sensory properties. A category prototype is that which is most likely recalled as the exemplar of the category, or that which is most cognitively economical at stimulating category recognition (see also; Eco 1976; Fodor 1998; Kenny 1994; Margolis & Lawrence 1999; Martindale 1990; Pinker 1997; Rey 1999; Rosch 1999; Simon 1996 for general reading on the subject of Concepts, Categorisation and Prototypes and Shackleton 1996, for its study in product design; Franzen & Bouwman 2001, marketing; Barnes & Zhi-Qiang 2004; Castelfranchi 2003, robotics and artificial intelligence).

assessments, whether the concepts are *combined* or not. The model works by first establishing all the possible properties of a concept through listing (via multiple sources) concept descriptors (typically adjectives) followed by a distribution into property ‘constructs’ (collectors of similar meaning). Property saliency is taken as the number of mentions of a descriptor equal to 1 mention = 1 ‘vote’. Property ‘diagnosticity’ is the measure of discrimination of the concept property verses other concept properties and is derived through an n by x table, whereby n is the number of property constructs and x the number of features assessed. Diagnosticity values (v) are then calculated through the formula;

$$v = (x^2 / N \min(A-1, B-1))^{1/2}$$

Where x^2 equals chi square, N the total number of constructs, A the number of rows and B the number of columns. Table 1 shows the layout of the property votes and prototype diagnosticity values for the concept APPLE. (Smith et. al. 1988).

Diagnosticity value	Construct	Descriptor Observed	Descriptor
1	Colour	25	red
		5	green
			brown
0.5	Shape	15	round
		0	square
		5	cylindrical
0.25	Texture	25	smooth
		5	rough
		0	bumpy

Table 1. Diagnosticity layout for the concept APPLE (Smith et. al. 1988).

Following the identification of property diagnosticity values and property saliency, typicality comparisons can be made according to Tversky’s ‘Contrast Principle’ (Margolis & Lawrence 1999), whereby similarity / dissimilarity is compared to a concepts prototype properties, here represented by a minor modification to Tversky’s original formula given by Smith et. al (1988);

$$Sim(I,J) = E; [afi(I \cap J) - bf(I - J) - cf(J - I)]$$

Where i is the index of properties, $I \cap J$ the set of common property 'votes', $I - J$ the set of distinct prototype 'votes' and $J - I$ the set of distinct example 'votes'. Constants a, b and c are equal to the 'relative contribution' of the sets and f multiply's the property i by its prototype diagnosticity value. Margolis and Lawrence demonstrate typicality to the concept BIRD for examples ROBIN and CHICKEN keeping a, b, c and f at a value of 1 for simplicity. The prototype BIRD properties are given as; flies, sings, lays eggs, is small, nests in trees, eats insects. We can see, therefore, that ROBIN would score against these properties $6 - 0 - 0 = 6$ and CHICKEN $1 - 5 + 5 = 1$, suggesting that ROBIN is more typical of the concept BIRD than CHICKEN (Margolis & Lawrence 1999).

Hampton (2006) confirms that the Selective Modification Model should not be taken as a model for categorisation but can be successful for identifying typicality, despite both assessments being subject to the constructs of similarity. Categorisation is determined by the presence of absolute properties which when above a certain threshold trigger category membership. The Selective Modification Model, however, does not define thresholds, but *relative* values of similarity (Hampton 2006; Smith et. al. 1988). Our interest in these methods here is in the potential application to the identification of prototypical property diagnosticity and salience values for the concept BENTLEY. We propose, therefore, to follow within this paper an exploration of that element alone, although we keep an eye on its logical development to typicality comparison.

Heritage study

The value of promoting established brand foundations is clearly recognised within product management and marketing disciplines. Lindstrom advises; '*Your primary objective...should be to ensure that all historical links and associations connected to your brand are supported, (they are) the strongest competitive advantage of (the) brand*' (Lindstrom 2005). Further, we have seen that brand recognition and categorisation is based upon attained and experiential knowledge of the brand concept. Therefore, in the analysis of brand 'typicality', or in our case 'Bentleyness', it appears appropriate to draw reference to a lineage of products familiar to the viewer. At Bentley Motors a study to identify product properties and features that are typical to the brand was conducted, and according to the principles above, included examples from

the company's past product portfolio. A group of 160 associates of the company, both male and female, but with a heavy engineering bias, was selected to review a collection of vehicles and photographs categorised by vehicle features and properties, including, for example, 'Exterior and Interior Lighting', 'Glazing', 'Exterior and Interior Handles', 'Colours', 'Veneers' and 'Seat Styles'. The photographs were pre-selected by the first, fourth and fifth authors, from a database of over 3000 examples and grouped into 36 feature categories with 12 examples in each category (see Fig.5 for two examples from the categories 'Airvents' and 'Instruments'). The collection of vehicles was sourced from Bentley Lineage with examples from the 1930's through to the 1990's, including production cars and bespoke Royal vehicles. Participants were encouraged to assess properties through visual cues and other sensory stimuli and then asked to identify their top seven features which, to them, most represented the concept BENTLEY from the photographic collection, and their top three from the vehicle collection. In asking for an explanatory note about the chosen features, significant quantities of adjective based descriptions of the properties were also collected.

The background research lead us to expect that some product properties are more or less important in the stimulation of the identification of the concept BENTLEY, and that 'prototype effects' may be evident. Also, we expected that *if* certain properties were more or less important in that stimulation, they would be *differently* important (scaled) for different product properties. As we have discussed, for the custodians of product properties that promote cognitive constructs of brand typicality, such conclusions would be advantageous; through understanding these concepts we propose it may be possible to influence the forward projection of new branded products and therefore also, consumer satisfaction relative to consumers associative beliefs, values and emotions.

Fig. 5. 'Bulls-eye' Airvent and Tachometer with clock; feature examples from the Bentley Heritage Study photographic collection.

Analysis of the data collected took two forms; firstly a sum of votes for specific properties and features and secondly, a detailed analysis of feature property descriptions with diagnosticity calculations according to the Selective Modification Model, focused on the vehicle interior alone. The aim of conducting the first analysis was to identify which feature categories were exemplars of the concept BENTLEY and which, if any, category members could be identified as having perceptions of prototypicality. The aim of the second analysis was to identify which properties were most salient in stimulating the identification of typicality for different interior vehicle features.

Results of the analysis of photographic feature categories identified that there were distinct groups of high scoring features; those appearing more frequently in participants identifications of features most representing the concept BENTLEY, and therefore taken to be more popular amongst reviewers; supporting our expectation that certain features are more or less important in the identification of the concept. The top 10 scoring feature categories represented 49% of the total 1275 responses (Fig.6). These categories included feature categories such as ‘Luxury items’, ‘Veneer’ and ‘Brightware’, but are not all named due to commercial confidentiality.

Fig 6. Percentage of total responses received allocated to the Top 10 feature categories. Responses attributed to the top 4 of the 12 possible examples within each category shown hatched.

Also, within those feature categories, there were distinct exemplars present. For example, the top feature category ([1], Fig 6) attracted 85 responses with 81% of these allocated to 4 features from the 12 available. We propose, therefore, based upon likeliness of selection and cognitive efficiency principles, that those 4 examples are more prototypical of the feature reviewed than other examples present. Note also, in Fig. 6., how some feature categories on this basis included exemplars with stronger or weaker prototypicality effects; category 5 had 100% of responses determined by 4 of the 12 possible examples. A similar analysis of the vehicle collection showed that they were also distinctly ranked, with the top scoring example receiving 10% more responses than the next highest, suggesting that prototype effects exist within both the photographic and physical exhibits reviewed.

The first analysis also performed the function of ranking the prototypical features in preparation for the second analysis; 81% of all descriptors collected being allocated to the top 12 feature categories, with remaining categories having statistically insufficient numbers of descriptors to analyse. Following Selective Modification Model principles, the participants free-form explanations of features identified as being typical of the concept BENTLEY were analysed for adjectival descriptors. The feature categories were further reduced to 9 to include only those influencing our area of interest; the interior of the vehicle. To enable diagnosticity calculations for each feature category, the descriptors extracted from the responses were allocated a 'vote' towards a defining construct. For example, the feature 'Tool Kits' (feature [d], Table 2) included property descriptors 'ordered', 'simplicity', 'clean' and 'precise', which were allocated to the construct 'Precision'. Descriptors with total 'votes' below 5 were further collected into sub-constructs to make them significant, or were eliminated from the analysis. Table 1 shows the diagnosticity values calculated for the 9 interior feature categories. Calculations made according to the Selective Modification Model demonstrate that individual feature properties are not equally important when diagnosing typicality for the concept BENTLEY, thus supporting Smith et. al.'s general findings, and our predictions in this application; constructs such as 'Precision' and 'Quality' are more salient when assessing prototypical Bentley 'Tool Kits', for example. The analysis also identified some unexpected properties; the property 'potency', for Tool Kits, has a high influence to the construct 'Character', suggesting that such properties, which express capabilities beyond basic requirements, or 'must-be' qualities, of the automotive product, are significant when assessing

some feature examples for typicality to the concept BENTLEY and are potentially one of the ‘attractive qualities’ of the brand.

Property				Feature	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
Diagnosticity value	Construct	Construct total Observed	Descriptor Observed	Descriptor									
10.907	Precision	61	14	ordered	1	1	2	8			2		
			32	simplicity	1	7	3	1	4	5	3	5	3
			6	clean			2	1	1				2
2.681	Hand crafted	44	9	precise				4			4	1	
			22	like furniture	21								1
			15	craftsmanship	9	1	2	1	1				1
			7	care	4				2				1
2.317	Refined	59	11	beautiful	3		1	1	1	2	3		
			21	elegant	4	4	4		3	2	2		2
			27	stylish	4	4	13		4	2	1	1	2
1.673	Comfort	30	21	comfortable		20							
			9	armchair		9							
1.046	Character	5	5	expressive		1	2			2			
			10	sporty		3	4				2		1
			5	potency				5					
			5	character	2	1	1			1			
0.743	Quality	23	15	quality			2	8	1			2	2
			8	appealing	6			1		1			
0.697	Luxurious	19	9	luxury	3	4			2				
			6	rich	1	1		1				1	2
			4	jewellery	1			1		1		1	
0.398	Structure	14	5	solid	2		1			1		1	
			9	strong	1	1				3		2	2
0.385	Form	39	11	size	7	2			2				
			7	form	7								
			11	flowing	6				1	3		1	
			10	graphic	2				2		3	1	2
0.188	Practicality	26	9	functional		4	2			2		1	
			7	practical			3	1		2	1		
			10	utility				5			1	4	
0.175	Bespoke	28	9	branding	2		2	4	1				
			11	individual	3		2	3	1	1			1
			8	distinct	1	1		1	2	1	1	1	
0.165	Lineage	19	11	class		1	4			2	1		3
			8	pedigree		4	3					1	
0.044	Sensory	16	6	soft		1	2		1		1	1	
			5	tactile		1		1		1		2	
			5	metallic							4	1	
0.010	Detailing	33	17	detailed				7	4	2		1	3
			16	intricate	14				2				
					101	71	55	54	35	34	30	28	28

Table 2. Analysis of adjectival descriptors collected for interior feature categories and the calculation of diagnosticity values.

Further applications

Following the principles proposed by Smith et. al. (1988) and Tversky (1977), similarity to the category prototype can be assessed using the diagnostic values identified, applied within the Contrast Principle methodology; their studies were seen as successful in identifying similarity scores for a number of ‘basic’ concepts including BIRD and APPLE. For more

complex concepts like BENTLEY, little research has been conducted into the measurement of typicality to a prototype. We propose, therefore, that further research would include similar review processes to that described above, with current and / or future branded product concepts in order to define and refine the application and to assess consumer satisfaction through measured associative cognitive constructs that evoke an ‘authenticity’ perception.

Conclusions

We have discussed the prevalent differentiating product properties of vehicles in the high-luxury and ‘pinnacle’ market segments and have shown that, over time, ‘attractive [product] qualities’ have become brand-based and associated with the expression of personal beliefs, values and emotions. We have used an adapted version of the Kano model to illustrate the evolution of quality in the automotive market place over the past two decades. We have also shown that, most importantly for the luxury and ‘pinnacle’ markets, those associations are rooted in a lineage of product designs that reinforce and extend brand identities. Research into cognitive processing theories has been referenced to show how recognition of a concept being a typical (best fit) member of a category, is perceived through the receipt of multi sensory stimuli. We refer, within the paper, to the prevailing theory of concept categorisation in relationship to brands; that branding forms part of the properties of a product within a product category. For example; the brand concept BENTLEY is associated with multi-sensory properties of a product that fits within the high-luxury and ‘pinnacle’ auto categories. We note also, however, that there is some evidence to suggest that *some* brands are, in themselves, ‘natural’ categories (Franzen & Bouwman 2001) e.g.: there are certain sets of multi-sensory properties that make certain products fit within the category we call BENTLEY. This hypothesis appears significant when considering branded product prototypicality and cognitive processing because it proposes to emphasise brand category property stimulation *rather than* product category property stimulation (see as yet unpublished work by the first and second authors which explores this hypothesis further).

Building on the market and scientific research foundations, we have proposed that to design and engineer successful product evolutions, which satisfy prevalent attractive product qualities, an understanding of the diagnosis of typicality to a prototype would be helpful. In conducting a focus group study of heritage properties at Bentley Motors Limited, quantitative

and qualitative data was gathered enabling identification of exemplars of the concept BENTLEY and an analysis of prototypicality for features and sub-systems around the car. Using the Selective Modification Model (Smith et. al. 1988), feature and sub-system properties that stimulated perceived fit between brand and product were analysed to be variable (different) between features and weighted (have a scaled importance).

We propose that values identified for the ‘diagnosticity’ of the concept BENTLEY, by feature, could be used to further extend this research to assess typicality and ‘authenticity’ for new concepts through the application of the second stage of Tyversky’s Contrast Principle (Margolis & Lawrence 1999), and could be combined with other quantitative and qualitative analyses from cognitive science and marketing as a guide to brand management and the engineering of emotional product identities in high-luxury vehicles.

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Acknowledgements

Dr. Ulrich Eichhorn, Mark Tennant, Chris Devane, Peter Herath